

IN-SITU SCANNING ACOUSTIC MICROSCOPY AND MODELING OF MICROSCOPIC DAMAGE PROGRESS IN CFRP LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In-situ observation of microscopic damage progress in CFRP laminated composites under static tensile loading is conducted by an scanning acoustic microscope (SAM) as well as an optical microscope (OM). Material systems are toughened-type CFRP (T800H/3631), and newly developed CFRP (T800H/3900-2) with selectively toughened interlaminar layers. By combining SAM and OM observations, it is possible to make quantitative measurement of damage progress in CFRP laminates, which is essential to the damage progress modeling.

INTRODUCTION

For more extensive use of CFRP for the primary structures, a damage tolerance design has to be introduced. The damage tolerance design will be only possible when a methodology for the prediction of the onset and growth of microscopic damage and the appropriate selection and employment of nondestructive inspection are available. However, the damage tolerance design is far from realizing mainly because damage progress modeling based on precise observation is not well established.

Masters and Reifsnider [1] investigated cumulative damage development in quasi-isotropic graphite/epoxy laminates. Transverse cracking in all off-axis laminae, longitudinal cracking, and delamination were monitored by the surface replication technique. They found that saturation crack patterns observed were unique for each lamina in the laminate (characteristic damage state, CDS).

Takeda et al. [2] conducted *in-situ* SAM observation to characterize the microscopic damage progress under tensile loading in injection-molded short fiber reinforced

thermoplastic composites. Quantitative load levels were determined for micromechanical fracture events.

It is important to observe microscopic damage progress precisely. Especially, *in-situ* observation is essential because it gives information about the location of damage initiation and the direction of damage growth. It also gives a basis for a quantitative measurement of damage. The objective of the present study is to establish a methodology for modeling the onset and growth behavior of the microscopic damage in the CFRP laminated composites as a basis for damage tolerance design.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

MATERIALS

Material systems are toughened-type CFRP (T800H/3631), and newly developed CFRP (T800H/3900-2) with selectively toughened interlaminar layers. The T800H/3900-2 prepreg system has tough and fine polyamide particles on its surfaces, which results in formation of the tough interlaminar layers in the laminates. The laminate configurations are cross-ply (0/90_m/0), where m=4, 8, and 12, for T800H/3900-2, and quasi-isotropic (0/45/90/-45)_{2s} for T800H/3631.

IN-SITU SAM OBSERVATIONS

In order to make *in-situ* observations, a tensile loading device is made which can be attached to the stage of the SAM (Olympus, UH-3). The device was first developed for *in-situ* SAM observation by using the 200MHz - 800MHz burst signals. In the present study, the device is reconstructed for SAM observations by using 30MHz pulse signals to detect damages inside laminates.

Figure 1 shows schematic illustration of the loading device. With the device, *in-situ* observations of microscopic damage progress can be made. A new high-number of aperture (HA) 30MHz pulse lens is employed, which uses a transverse wave as well as a longitudinal wave [3]. This HA pulse lens (100-degree aperture angle) has several characteristics different from a normal lens (30-degree aperture angle). Particularly, transverse cracks in CFRP laminates can be detected by the HA pulse lens [3, 4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

T800H/3900-2 CROSS-PLY LAMINATES

Figure 2 shows edge damage state in T800H/3900-2 cross-ply (0/90₄/0) laminate observed by an optical microscope (780MPa). The first microscopic damage observed

in the laminate is transverse cracks in 90° layer. The number of transverse cracks increases as load increases, but delamination at the tips of the transverse cracks is not observed unlike T800H/3631 cross-ply laminates [5, 6]. It is due to the enhancement of interlaminar toughness by the polyamide particle-dispersed layers.

Figure 3 shows a SAM image (30MHz HA pulse lens) of T800H/3900-2 cross-ply (0/90₄/0) laminate (780MPa). The SAM image was obtained by observing 0°/90° interface through the outer 0° ply. Transverse cracks running through the width of the specimen are observed as interference patterns which are similar to the simulation results [3].

Figure 4 shows transverse crack density as a function of applied laminate stress in 90° ply. For the laminates with thicker 90° ply, the transverse crack density at laminate fracture is smaller.

Takeda and Ogihara proposed a model predicting the relationship between the applied laminate strain and the transverse crack density, making use of the statistical parameters of experimentally-obtained 90° UD strength distribution[5]. The 90° ply in the cross-ply laminate is divided into elements which are assumed to fail only once up to the ultimate failure. The strength distribution of the elements is assumed to obey the same two-parameter Weibull distribution as measured for the transverse strength of UD. The transverse crack density ρ is expressed as a function of the laminate strain, ϵ_0 , by

$$\rho = \frac{1}{L_e} \left[1 - \exp \left\{ -V_e \left(\frac{E_2(\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_2^T - \epsilon_c)}{\alpha_s} \right)^\beta \right\} \right] \quad (1)$$

where L_e and V_e are element length and volume, respectively. E_2 is Young's modulus of 90° ply, and ϵ_2^T is thermal residual strain in 90° ply. α_s and β are Weibull scale and shape parameters, respectively. ϵ_c is the difference between the first cracking strain predicted by the energy criterion and the first cracking strain predicted by the strength criterion.

A comparison of the predictions of transverse crack density and experimental results is shown in Fig.4 [7]. The present probabilistic approach shows good agreement with the experimental results.

T800H/3631 QUASI-ISOTROPIC LAMINATES

Figure 5 shows edge damage state in T800H/3631 quasi-isotropic (0/45/90/-45)_{2s} laminate observed by an optical microscope ((a) 684MPa, (b) 729MPa). The first microscopic damage observed in the laminate is transverse cracks in 90° layer. As the load increases, the number of transverse cracks in 90° layer increases. Transverse cracks in -45° layer occurs at lower load level than those in 45 layer as shown later in Fig.4. As shown in Fig.5 (b), extensive edge delamination occurs at 729MPa. By

optical microscopy, it is impossible to know how the edge delamination propagates in the specimen width direction.

Figure 6 shows SAM images (30MHz HA pulse lens) of T800H/3631 quasi-isotropic $(0/45/90/-45)_{2s}$ laminate ((a) 684MPa, (b) 729MPa). Small edge delamination is observed at 684MPa, and extensive delamination is observed at 729 MPa.

Figure 7 shows the transverse crack density as a function of applied laminate stress in each off-axis ply obtained by the optical microscope observation.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In-situ observation of microscopic damage progress in CFRP laminated composites under static tensile loading is conducted by an scanning acoustic microscope (SAM) as well as an optical microscope (OM). By combining SAM and OM observations, it is possible to make quantitative measurement of damage progress in CFRP laminates, which is essential to the damage progress modeling.

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Figure 1. Schematic Illustration of the Tensile Loading Device for *In-Situ* Observation Attached to the Stage of a Scanning Acoustic Microscope (SAM).

Figure 2. Edge Damage State in T800H/3900-2 Cross-Ply (0/90₄/0) Laminate Observed by an Optical Microscope (780MPa).

Figure 3. *In-Situ* SAM Image (30MHz HA pulse lens) of T800H/3900-2 Cross-Ply (0/90₄/0) Laminate (780MPa).

Figure 4. Transverse Crack Density as a Function of Applied Laminate Stress for T800H/3900-2 (0/90_m/0).

Figure 7. Transverse Crack Density in Each Off-Axis Layer as a Function of Applied Laminate Stress for T800H/3631(0/45/90/-45)_{2s}.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Edge Damage State in T800H/3631 Quasi-Isotropic $(0/45/90/-45)_{2s}$ Laminate Observed by an Optical Microscope ((a) 684MPa, (b) 729MPa).

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. *In-Situ* SAM Images (30MHz HA Pulse Lens) of T800H/3631 Quasi-Isotropic (0/45/90/-45)_{2s} Laminate ((a) 684MPa, (b) 729MPa).